

FORMATION OF PUBLIC GOODS BY AGRICULTURE IN SMOLYAN DISTRICT, BULGARIA

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Abstract

The production of goods for the market may include aspects of public goods, for example when the production of certain agricultural products or landscapes created by farms are part of a local identity. A kind of public good is the local culture that is often associated with farming.

The aim of the study is to assess the provision of agriculture to the formation of public goods and the factors to optimize this process.

The finding of the research is that the agricultural sector in Smolyan region is actively involved in the provision of public goods, which are highly appreciated by the local farmers. An important part of the process of provisioning public goods is their proper combination with market goods, which will contribute to gain a competitive advantage of the region. Farmers expect support from public institutions to explore these competitive advantages. In this way, supporting the development of business that has the character of private interest will also maintain the public goods in the region.

Key words: public goods, water quality, food security, scenery

Zusammenfassung

Die Produktion von Gütern für den Markt kann Aspekte öffentlicher Güter umfassen, beispielsweise wenn die Produktion bestimmter landwirtschaftlicher Produkte oder von landwirtschaftlichen Betrieben geschaffene Landschaften Teil einer lokalen Identität sind. Eine Art öffentliches Gut ist die lokale Kultur, die oft mit der Landwirtschaft in Verbindung gebracht wird.

Ziel der Studie ist es, die Bereitstellung der Landwirtschaft für die Bildung öffentlicher Güter und die Faktoren zur Optimierung dieses Prozesses zu bewerten.

Das Ergebnis der Untersuchung ist, dass der Agrarsektor in der Region Smoljan aktiv an der Bereitstellung öffentlicher Güter beteiligt ist, die von den lokalen Bauern sehr geschätzt werden. Ein wichtiger Teil des Prozesses der Bereitstellung öffentlicher Güter ist ihre richtige Kombination mit Marktgütern, die dazu beitragen wird, einen Wettbewerbsvorteil der Region zu erlangen. Die Landwirte erwarten von öffentlichen Institutionen Unterstützung bei der Erforschung dieser Wettbewerbsvorteile. Auf diese Weise wird die Unterstützung der Entwicklung von Unternehmen, die den Charakter eines privaten Interesses haben, auch die öffentlichen Güter in der Region erhalten.

Schlüsselwörter: öffentliche Güter, Wasserqualität, Ernährungssicherheit, Landschaft

Résumé

La production de biens destinés au marché peut inclure des aspects de biens publics, par exemple lorsque la production de certains produits agricoles ou de paysages créés par des exploitations agricoles fait partie d'une identité locale. Une sorte de bien public est la culture locale qui est souvent associée à l'agriculture.

L'objectif de l'étude est d'évaluer l'apport de l'agriculture à la formation de biens publics et les facteurs permettant d'optimiser ce processus.

Les résultats de l'étude montrent que le secteur agricole de la région de Smolyan est activement impliqué dans la fourniture de biens publics, qui sont très appréciés par les agriculteurs locaux. Une partie importante du processus de fourniture des biens publics est leur combinaison adéquate avec les biens du marché, ce qui contribuera à obtenir un avantage compétitif de la région. Les agriculteurs attendent des institutions publiques qu'elles les aident à explorer ces avantages compétitifs. De cette façon, le soutien au développement d'entreprises ayant un caractère d'intérêt privé permettra également de maintenir les biens publics dans la région.

Mots clés: biens publics, qualité de l'eau, sécurité alimentaire, paysage

Introduction

The term "public good" in the context of farming systems is often associated with the concept of multifunctionality, which recognizes "the simultaneous consideration of the various positive and negative effects of agriculture and their joint production externality aspects of public good" (OECD, 2001). Some types of public goods are produced in systems designed specifically for their provision (eg health and social infrastructure), others may be regarded as byproducts of systems whose main purpose is the production of private goods. Such is the case of public goods from agriculture and forestry. In this regard, certain goods can be classified as public goods because of their economic nature (eg attractive landscape) and others such

Production of goods for the market could include aspects of public goods such as production of certain agricultural products or created farm landscapes are part of the local identity (Marinov, P., 2017). A kind of public good is itself a local culture that is most often associated with agricultural activities. Therefore agriculture is often viewed as a repository of typical local cultures (Stoeva and Valcheva, 2016). They occur in food, agricultural practices, language, music, etc. In this context, the EU pays special attention to the importance of diverse European rural culture to support rural development and contribute to agro-biological diversity. Defiantly is to establish the link between market goods and public goods resulting from agricultural activity. For example, local foods with added value and cultural landscape represent markets and society benefit from this local culture. Thus, although it is difficult to measure, the agricultural sector has an impact on the formation of public goods which can be used to improve market status of farmers (Zahoalij and Kolaj, 2017).

The aim of the study is to assess the provision of agriculture to the formation of public goods and the factors to optimize this process.

To study the provision of public goods by agriculture sector, were interviewed 30 farmers from Smolyan District, Bulgaria. Their production activity is focused on the cultivation of beans, potatoes and

sheep-breeding that are typical for the region, and produces agricultural products, formed almost exclusively agricultural incomes and have built an image of the region. Appropriate conditions for production and traditions in these proceedings are popular among the local community, while consumers evaluate products manufactured here as quality and natural. These industries also have a strong influence on the formation of rural landscapes and the provision of public goods for local people and visitors to the region.

Results

Respondents farmers according to gender affiliation is allocated at a ratio of 2:1 in favor of males (see Fig. 1). The larger relative of men gender is explained by the fact that the region's business including and agriculture are managed by men and thus the sample faithfully represents the economic reality. Also agriculture in the region is mountainous and production activities are carried out manually and often require physical strength that is inherent in the male sex.

Figure 1. Gender of farmers. Source: Own survey, 2018

Interest is the distribution of respondents according to their age. It had sought an even distribution, but farming is dealing mainly older people, which is why the sample largest share have persons over 55 years, their number exceeds almost 3 times that of persons under 34 years (Fig. 2). However, we believe that the results of the polls will have its weight in terms that examine farmers who richer life experience and possess a strong sense of belonging to the region and its typical characteristics.

Figure 2. Age of farmers. Source: Own survey, 2018

Another important feature of the respondents is the time from when dealing with agriculture. This indicator distribution in three groups - new agricultural holdings (created at many years ago) holdings aged between 1 and 5 years, farms operating for more than five years. The largest share of respondents have farms of over five years - more than half are members of this group. The remaining two groups are represented approximately equally, with a slightly larger proportion have holdings aged between 1 and 5 years. This sample provides an opportunity to explore the farms with different experiences.

Figure 3. Age of business. Source: Own survey, 2018

Respondents indicate that advisory services for nearly half of them resort to consultation at least once a month (Fig. 4). The majority of farmers used less frequently consultations, which practically means that seeking advice once, at most twice during a single production cycle. This is explained by the fact that manufacturers are mostly small in size and production can not allocate financial resources to attract consultants to advise them in every stage of production. Therefore, seek informal contacts for consultation and seeking solutions to deal with problems.

Figure 4. Use frequency of consultancy services. Source: Own survey, 2018

An important characteristic of the research population is the realization of other economic activities of farmers. More than half said that developing and other business activities difrent from agriculture (Fig. 5). These individuals indicated that agriculture is actually not the main source of income

for them, and there are more in the nature of an additional source. This is due to the fact that the share of income from agricultural activities formed to 1/3 of their total annual income.

Figure 5. Non-agricultural activities. Source: Own survey, 2018

The educational level of the respondents is extremely high, nearly 90% of them have higher education (Fig. 6). This is an indicator giving reason to expect that farmers have a complex overview of the dimensions of their business and can determine its impact on the local economy and society as a whole.

Figure 6. Education of farmers. Source: Own survey, 2018

Ineteres represents the presence of heir to continue the farm. Nearly half of respondents stated that they expect to be inherited (Fig. 7). The share of those who firmly stated that no one can possess them is small, which means that the prospects industry to preserve good. However large percentage answered evasively "do not know" means that the leading factor for storage of agricultural production will be more current environment and opportunities for development of such business than traditional or other emotional response patterns.

Figure 7. Successor of agricultural business. Source: Own survey, 2018

All respondents said they did not participate in agri-environment payments and produce products with clear identification of origin. Therefore, do not form income and expenses related to the implementation of commitments in these areas.

Farmers were asked to evaluate the contribution of agriculture to provide three public goods - quality and availability of water; food security; scenery and recreation. The results show that farmers determine that agriculture plays an important role in shaping food security and create attractive landscapes and opportunities for recreation (figure 8). This is because the region is famous for its agricultural products (lima beans, potatoes Momchilovtsi, sheep milk and lamb), which can be described as iconic and have a positive impact on the overall image of the region. It is noteworthy that does not establish a similar opinion about the impact of agriculture on the quality and quantity of water. This explains that farmers do not develop irrigated agriculture and use of fertilizers limited. Also, the amount of production plots is small, suggesting an inability to concentrate compounds that can significantly impact the water sources.

Figure 8. Support of agriculture to creation of public goods - water, food, recreation. Source: Own survey, 2018

Already it mentioned that the region has suitable conditions for development of agricultural production set - beans, potatoes and sheep. However, nearly one third of respondents define the image of these products as a weak or absent (Fig. 9), which is surprising against the background of the positive user review. Yet no small part by the farmers appreciate the image of local products as high, which enables to produce products with clear identification of origin.

Respondents rated and opportunities to produce products without or with clear identification of origin. Both alternatives have been considered as a basis for obtaining benefits in four key areas - benefits; opportunities; expenses; risk. Benefits are looking for in terms of higher profits for farmers proizvoditeli, providing more secure guarantees to consumers about food safety, preservation of natural resources and maintaining an attractive environment.

Opportunities are identified by facilitating access to markets through participation in clusters, storage of local communities and traditions, improve the landscape. The costs relate to those associated with the realization of the products on the market, training costs of manufacturers to comply with standards, introduction of environmental standards.

Figure 9. Market image of local products. Source: Own survey, 2018

The risks stem from the fact that introducing new products and the market needs time to accept it (economic risk), agriculture is a traditional sector and the products must not be contrary to established traditions (social risk), water protection as important representative of public goods also depends on the chosen technology of production (environmental risk). The assessment was again done in 4 point scale, with a higher score indicating a strong contribution of the alternative to achieve the advantages described above. The sum of the scores of all respondents determines the overall score for each direction, the maximum value is 810 points. The alternative to produce products with clear identification of origin is assessed as an opportunity to realize the benefits described in all directions. This alternative (al 2) receives estimates exceeding more than 2 times the evaluations of the other alternative, which is evidence for its recognition by farmers as a good opportunity to promote and improve local production and the natural environment (Fig. 10). While respondents are aware that the implementation of this alternative requires additional effort and expenditure by farmers, which ultimately increases the risk associated with its successful implementation.

Figure 10. Evaluation of two alternatives to gain benefits (max. Score 810). Source: Own survey, 2018
al 1 - without identification of origin; al 2 - with identification of origin

Interviewees identified and which public goods should be financed as a priority through the mechanisms of the CAP. I evaluated 10 public goods (Fig. 11). As the most important the following are five - to improve the durability of floods, landslides and fires; food safety and quality assurance; mitigate climate problems; maintaining the vitality of rural areas and communities; improving air quality. All they receive assessments interavala 80-90 points are the maximum possible. These public goods correspond to the fundamental problems of rural areas whose solution can hardly be achieved only through market mechanism. Three other public goods - maintaining the quality and quantity of water; maintaining the functionality of the soil; ensure local supplies are rated between 70 and 80 points. Least been evaluated creation of atraktivin rural landscapes and maintain farmland biodiversity.

Also, all respondents determine the amount of 80 euros annual payment per household as sufficient to encourage the provision of public goods.

Figure 11. Priority of public goods in financial support (max. Score 90). Source: Own survey, 2018

Through statistical method chi-square we found the interactions of three public goods with socio-economic variables of local farmers (see Table 1).

Table 1. Results from testing the statistically significant relationship between the characteristics of the farmers and public goods. Source: Own survey, 2018

	Water	food	Recreation
Gender	no relation	no relation	there is a realation
Age	there is a realation	no relation	there is a realation
Experience	there is a realation	no relation	no relation
Consultancy	no relation	no relation	there is a realation
Non agricultural activities	there is a realation	no relation	no relation
Education	no relation	no relation	no relation
Successor	there is a realation	no relation	no relation

Maintaining water quality is part of the activities of farmers who are older age, have more experience as farmers, carry out another business and have someone to inherit their business. Obviously the benefits of public good look in the long term, the goal is to ensure sustainability of the environment for business and life. The possibilities of Agriculture to create conditions for recreation is assessed by women farmers, older farmers and those who use advisory services. In this context can be interpreted relationship between agriculture and tourism and to achieve synergistic effects from their interaction. Interesting is the fact that for the third public good "food security" no relationship with any of the studied characteristics of the farmers. This gives grounds to look for other motivating factors that affect the provision of this public good. We can assume that the market is a priority influence on the development of food security.

Conclusion

The results and findings lead to the conclusion that the agricultural sector in Smolyan region actively participated in the formation of public goods that are highly valued by local farmers. Public goods in the region are a direct result of land management, whichever is the high level in this region.

An important part of the process of providing public goods is the proper combination to market products that will ensure that the competitive advantage of the region. Public goods have an important role in shaping the competitive advantages of the region. They assist businesses in creating value in their business and market development. Offering products with clear identification of origin is complemented by local public goods, thereby achieving uniqueness of the proposed value.

Farmers expect support from the public institutions to absorb these competitive advantages. Thus, supporting the development of business, the nature of a private interest will be maintained and public goods in the region.

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